

**A STUDY COMPUTER APPLICATIONS EFFECTIVENESS IN ACADEMIC
ADMINISTRATION BY TEACHERS AMONG COLLEGES
AFFILIATED TO NORTH MAHARASHTRA
UNIVERSITY, JALGAON**

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Abstract:-

Since last few years many Universities and Higher education Institutions in Maharashtra are using Computers and I.C.T. in Academic Administrations. The North Maharashtra University is also using Computer application for Academic Administration. The University is using OAASIS. It is necessary to make a survey and study. How effectively the College Teachers are using OAASIS for Examination and Affiliation purpose. Majority 56.2% college teachers rated as Good .

Introduction:-

The Maharashtra Knowledge Corporation Limited (MKCL) had developed a Computer Application Online Academic Administration System and Information Services (OAASIS) for Academic Administration among colleges and Universities of Maharashtra State. The North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon is also using OAASIS and had made it compulsory to all affiliated colleges and Institutes for using OAASIS. It is expected that the Teachers from Colleges and Institutes Should accept Examination appointment and respond to it. The teachers should download their appointment on Local Enquiry Committees and all related information of concern college through OAASIS. The present study focus on how effectively the teachers from Colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University are using OAASIS for responding to their appointments regarding Examination work. And how effectively the teachers from Colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University are using OAASIS for downloading their appointments on LIC regarding affiliation work.

Material and Method :-

During the period of 2015-16 this survey was done. Primary data is collected from various Teachers associated with colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University with the help of structured questionnaire. The research practices are comprise of random sampling, data collection, data editing, data classification, tabulation and interpretation of data with the

help of statistical tools.

Observation and result-

Table 1. How Teachers are responding to examination appointments

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
How Teachers are Responding to examination appointments	Very Good	272	31.9
	Good	480	56.2
	Average	98	11.5
	Poor	4	0.5

Figure 1 : How Teachers are responding to examination appointments

- **Table 2: Downloading Local Inquiry Committee appointments for affiliation**

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Downloading Local Inquiry Committee appointments for affiliation	Very Good	218	25.5
	Good	514	60.2
	Average	116	13.6
	Poor	4	0.5
	Very Poor	2	0.2

Figure 24 : Downloading Local Inquiry Committee appointments for affiliation

The responses of the college teachers when they requested to rate How teachers are responding to examination appointments 31.9% college teachers rated as Very Good, majority 56.2% college teachers rated as Good, 11.5% college teachers rated as Average and only 0.5% college teachers rated as Poor.

The responses of the college teachers when they requested to rate the how frequently the are downloading Local Inquiry Committee appointments for affiliation. 25.5% college teachers rated as Very Good, majority 60.2% college teachers rated as Good, 13.6% college teachers rated as Average, only 0.5% college teachers rated as Poor and negligible 0.2% college teachers rated as Very Poor.

Discussion-

it is observe that majority of Teachers are using Computer application in academic administration. Majority of Teacher are satisfied with OAASIS. To increase the effective use of OAASIS, it is recommended to organize orientation programs for Teachers.

Refrencess:-

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